

Phase-based Cyclic Time Series Forecasting

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Keywords:

1. INTRODUCTION, AIM, MATERIALS AND METHODS, RESULTS

State space models are popular tools in modeling time series as a noisy function of some unobservable process, called the state process. A special family of state space models that are additive and Gaussian is called dynamic linear models. These models are often used to capture the time series as the sum of multiple components subject to an observational noise. These components usually include a trend, a seasonal, and a regression model that are added together as main blocks of the model. A seasonal pattern is used to model the influence of seasonal factors and is always of a fixed and known period. In business time series, however, the business cycles often consist of multiple serial phases that occur in changing periods. Therefore, business data usually exhibit fluctuations that are not of fixed periods. In this article, we propose a transformation of time that helps forecast phase-based cyclic patterns in time series using dynamic linear models. This transformation poses unequal variances to observation and evolution noises of the business time series. We propose a weighted noise structure for the dynamic linear model to overcome this challenge.

2. Conclusions

Business processes do not always follow regular patterns that map neatly to calendar time. A major business cycle, such as the serial development and release of major versions of software products, can follow this somewhat irregular pattern. Further, business cycles themselves may consist of multiple serial phases of unequal duration where the beginning of a phase depends on the completion of the prior phase. As a result, business data often exhibit cyclic patterns that are associated with phase-based cycles rather than calendar-based cycles. Multiple factors such as operational bugs and human errors can delay the completion of a phase, which also delays the beginning of the following phase. Hence, the business cycle often occurs in changing periods which prevents existing dynamic linear models from accurately modeling the associated phase-based cyclic pattern. The primary focus of this paper is to develop a general framework for forecasting cyclic patterns of a phase-based cycle data using dynamic linear models.

Dynamic linear models are often constructed by combining multiple components in which each component captures a specific feature of the time series. These components typically include a trend and a seasonal that are combined together in an additive fashion. Seasonal

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components, though, are usually based on the assumption that the seasonal pattern is of a fixed period, and cannot be used to model a changing business cyclic pattern. To model the cyclic pattern of a phase-based cycle data, we propose normalized time as a transformation of time that is defined such that each phase has the same duration, measured in the new basis, in all cycles. We show that, as a result of the proposed transformation, the time series data might have multiple observations for which the corresponding normalized time has the same value. We then use the average of these multiple observations to define the normalized time series. We prove a theorem that shows the proposed transformation poses unequal variances to observation and evolution noises of the trend of normalized time series. This theorem also provides a weighted noise structure for the trend component of the model.

3. Keywords

State space models; dynamic linear models; seasonal; cyclic; additive; trend

Author biography

Sol Sadeghi Sol Sadeghi is a data scientist II in WDG Core Data Science team at Microsoft. He has a PhD in Statistics with a minor in Computer Science from the University of Wisconsin-Madison. He also has a MS in Statistics from the University of Florida and a BS in Industrial Engineering from Sharif University of Technology. He joined Microsoft in June 2017 and is currently working on cyclic time series forecasting.